

**PHARMAAYURVED ONLINE RESEARCH JOURNAL
FOR PHARMACY, AYURVED AND ALLIED SCIENCES**

<http://www.pharmaayurved.in/>

***ASTHI DHATU AND ITS CORRELATION WITH THE SKELETAL SYSTEM: AN
AYURVEDIC AND MODERN PERSPECTIVE***

Authors:

1. Dhara V. Patel, Assistant Professor, Department Of Rachana Sharira, S.S. Agrawal institute of Ayurveda, Navsari, Gujarat-396445

Citation: Dhara V. Patel, (2026).

***ASTHI DHATU AND ITS CORRELATION WITH THE SKELETAL
SYSTEM: AN AYURVEDIC AND MODERN PERSPECTIVE.*** In

Pharmaayurved Online Research Journal (Vol.10, Issue 1, pp. 506–511).

Pharmaayurved Online Research Journal. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18730569>

Corresponding author: Dr. Dhara V. Patel

Email: drdhara97@gmail.com

- **Article Received on: 17-02-26**
- **Accepted on: 20-02-26**
- **Published on: 22-02-26**

Abstract

Introduction:

Ayurveda describes the human body through seven fundamental tissues known as *Sapta Dhātu*. Among them, *Asthi Dhātu* provides structural support, protection to vital organs, and stability to the body. Classical texts describe *Asthi* as derived from *Meda Dhātu* and closely associated with *Vata Dosha* and essential for locomotion and nourishment of *Majja Dhātu*. In modern science, these functions are attributed to the skeletal system.

Aim:

To study the concept of *Asthi Dhātu* as described in classical *Ayurvedic* texts and to correlate it with the modern anatomical and physiological understanding of the skeletal system in modern medicine.

Materials and Methods:

A conceptual and comparative literary review was conducted using classical *Ayurvedic* texts such as *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, and *Ashtanga Hridaya*, along with modern anatomy and physiology textbooks. Comparative analysis was performed to establish structural, functional and pathological correlations.

Results:

Asthi Dhātu exhibits close structural and functional resemblance to the skeletal system, including bones, teeth, cartilage, and related structures. Functions such as support, protection, movement, and mineral storage described in modern science align well with *Ayurvedic* descriptions. Disorders of *Asthi Dhātu* resemble degenerative and metabolic bone disorders described in modern medicine.

Key Words:

Asthi Dhātu, Skeletal System, *Sapta Dhātu*, *Ayurveda*, Bone Physiology

INTRODUCTION:

Ayurveda explains the human body as a functional unity of *Dosha*, *Dhatu*, and *Mala*. Total *Dhatus* are seven in number¹. According to *Ayurvedic* classics, *Asthi Dhatu* originates from *Meda Dhatu*² through the action of *Asthidhatvagni* and nourishes *Majja Dhatu*. It is the primary seat of *Vata Dosha* which governs movement and neuromuscular activities. Any imbalance in *Vata* directly affects *Asthi Dhatu*, leading to disorders like *Asthikshaya* and *Sandhivata*.

Asthi Dhatu is the fifth *Dhatu* in the sequence of *Sapta Dhatu* and is responsible for maintaining the body's framework (*Sharira Dharana*)³. *Asthi Dhatu* occupies an important position as it provides firmness (*Kathinya*), shape, and structural integrity to the body.

In modern anatomy, the skeletal system consists of bones, cartilage, joints, and associated structures that provide shape, support, protection, mineral storage, hematopoiesis and facilitate movement. This review attempts to establish a systematic correlation between these two concepts.

Materials and Methods

Materials

Classical *Ayurvedic* texts:

- *Charaka Samhita*
- *Sushruta Samhita*
- *Astanga Hridaya*

Modern textbooks:

- Gray's Anatomy
- Guyton and Hall Textbook of Medical Physiology
- Ganong's Review of Medical Physiology

Methods

- Review and interpretation of *Asthi Dhatu* in *Ayurvedic* literature
- Study of skeletal system anatomy and physiology
- Comparative analysis of structure, function, metabolism, and pathology

Aims and Objectives

To study the concept of *Asthi Dhatu* as described in classical *Ayurvedic* texts and to correlate it with the modern anatomical and physiological understanding of the skeletal system in modern medicine.

Results

➤ **Concept of *Asthi Dhatu* in *Ayurveda***

- *Asthi Dhatu* is defined as the tissue that provides firmness and stability to the body. It nourishes *Majja Dhatu* and is characterized by hardness (*Kathinya*), stability, and resistance. *Asthi Dhatu* is responsible for *Sharira Dharana*³ (maintenance of body structure).

➤ **Components of Asthi Dhatu (Ayurveda)**

- Bones (*Asthi*)
- Teeth (*Danta*)
- Nails (*Nakha*)
- Joints (*Sandhi*)
- Hair (*Kesha* – considered *mala* of *Asthi* by some *Acharyas*)

➤ **Correlation between Asthi Dhatu and Skeletal System**

Table 1: Structural Correlation⁴

<i>Asthi Dhatu (Ayurveda)</i>	Skeletal System (Modern)
<i>Asthi</i>	Bones
<i>Danta</i>	Teeth
<i>Sandhi</i>	Joints
<i>Upadhatu – Danta</i>	Enamel, dentin
<i>Asthi Mala – Kesha, Nakha</i>	Hair, Nails (keratinized structures)

Table 2: Functional Correlation⁵

Function of Asthi Dhatu	Skeletal System Function
<i>Sharira Dharana</i> (Body support)	Structural framework
<i>Majja Poshana</i>	Bone marrow protection

<i>Anga Rakshana</i>	Protection of organs
<i>Gati Sahaya</i>	Movement with muscles
<i>Vata Ashraya</i>	Regulation of movement

Table 3: *Asthi Kshaya* vs Bone Disorders⁶

<i>Asthi Kshaya (Ayurveda)</i>	Modern Correlation
<i>Asthi Shoola</i>	Bone pain
<i>Danta Bheda</i>	Tooth decay
<i>Nakha Kesha Prapatana</i>	Brittle nails, Hair fall
<i>Sandhi Shaithilya</i>	Osteoarthritis
<i>Daurbalya</i>	Osteoporosis

Discussion

Asthi Dhatu shares remarkable similarity with the skeletal system in terms of origin, structure, function, and pathology. *Ayurveda* emphasizes the role of Agni, nutrition, and *Vata* balance in maintaining *Asthi* health, while modern science focuses on minerals like calcium, phosphorus, vitamin D, and hormonal regulation.

The *Ayurvedic* concept of *Asthivaha Srotas* can be correlated with bone metabolism and remodeling processes. Disorders such as *Asthikshaya* show close resemblance to osteoporosis and age related degenerative bone diseases.

Understanding these correlations provides a holistic approach to bone health and validates *Ayurvedic* principles through modern scientific perspectives.

Conclusion

Asthi Dhatu represents the *Ayurvedic* counterpart of the skeletal system. Both systems emphasize support, protection, movement, and nourishment of deeper tissues. Correlating *Asthi Dhatu* with modern skeletal anatomy strengthens integrative medical knowledge and opens avenues for combined preventive and therapeutic strategies in bone-related disorders.

REFERENCES:

- 1) Sushruta Samhita, edited with “Susrutavimarsini” hindi commentary by Dr. Anant Ram Sharma, Acharya Priya Vrat Sharma, Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan, Varanasi; Sharira Sthana Sarir Sankhya Vyakaran Sharir Adhyaya 5/7, Page no.71.
- 2) Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita, edited with “Caraka-Chandrika” hindi commentary by Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan, Varanasi; Chikitsa Sthana Grahani Dosha Chikitsa Adhyaya 15/17–19, Page no. 463.
- 3) Vagbhata, Ashtanga Hridaya, edited with “Nirmala” Hindi Commentary by Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan, Sutra Sthana Doshadi Vigyaniya Adhyaya 11/4, Page no. 161.
- 4) Standring S, Gray’s Anatomy: The Anatomical Basis of Clinical Practice, 41st edition, Elsevier; 2016.
- 5) Guyton A.C., Hall J.E. Textbook of Medical Physiology, 14th edition. Elsevier; 2021.
- 6) Ganong W.F. Review of Medical Physiology, 26th edition, McGraw Hill; 2018.